

value of α , the Brönsted coefficient in the present case compared to the value of 0.50 reported by Mishra *et al*⁷ for the reaction of phenacyl bromide with benzoate ions indicates a greater degree of bond formation between the nucleophile and the reaction centre in the present case.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their grateful thanks to Prof. Sp. Shanmuganathan, Principal, Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry, Pachaiyappa's College, Madras for encouragement and facilities. Thanks are also due to Prof. B. R. Pai, Consultant, Research and Development, Amrutanjan Ltd., Madras for helpful suggestions and spectral data. Partial financial support of the University Grants Commission, New Delhi is also gratefully acknowledged.

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Terpenoids and Related Compounds.

Part XXX¹. The Configuration of the Hydroxyl Group of Putrol

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Manuscript received 24 December 1980, revised 1 June 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

SESHADRI *et al*² reported the isolation of two closely related triterpenoids belonging to the 25-norfriedooleanane series namely putrone and its corresponding alcohol putrol from the leaves of *Putranjiva roxburghii*. Based upon physical data these workers suggested the structure of putrone as 3-keto-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (I) and that of putrol as 3 α -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (II). But they did not correlate these compounds

with a compound of known structure and stereochemistry. It was recently shown³ in this laboratory by direct correlation with a known friedoolean derivative that the structure (I) suggested by Seshadri *et al* for putrone was indeed correct.

Seshadri *et al*² also reported that putrone (I) underwent easy reduction with sodium borohydride to form an alcohol which was found to be identical with putrol (II). On the other hand putrol when oxidised with chromic acid afforded putrone (I). But considering the known⁴⁻⁶ hydride reductions of various 3-keto friedooleanane derivatives in which the newly generated hydroxyl group at C-3 always assumes the β -axial configuration, we believed that the correct structure of putrol would be 3 β -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (III) and not 3 α -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (II) as suggested by Seshadri *et al*.

It is known^{7,8} that reduction of 3-ketofriedooleananes with sodium and amyl alcohol always gives the thermodynamically more stable 3 α (equatorial) alcohol. We therefore reduced putrone (I) with sodium and amyl alcohol to furnish the 3 α -hydroxy compound (II) which was found to be different (mixed m.p., co-tlc and ir) from natural putrol. Further the acetate (IV) of this 3 α alcohol was also found to be different from putryl acetate (V)² derived from natural putrol. Thus the correct structure of putrol was (III).

In support of the above contention, the nmr spectra of a number of 3 α (equatorial) and 3 β (axial) acetoxy friedooleananes have been studied. The signal of the axial proton at position C-3 carrying an α -acetoxy group invariably appeared as a multiplet(1H) centered around δ 4.60 to 4.62 ppm. But the signal of the equatorial proton at C-3 carrying a β -acetoxy group invariably appeared as a triplet(1H) in a comparatively downfield region centered around δ 4.87 to 4.90 ppm. The acetate (V) prepared from natural putrol showed a triplet(1H) around δ 4.90 ppm. This fact established beyond doubt that the proton at C-3 of (V) was α (equatorial). Obviously the hydroxyl group of putrol was β -axial. Our investigation also established that nmr spectra can be used to determine the absolute configuration of the hydroxyl group at C-3 of friedooleananes. The results are shown below in Table 1.

TABLE 1.—NMR SIGNALS EXHIBITED BY THE C-3 PROTON OF SOME 3-ACETOXYFRIEDOOLEANANES

Name of the 3-acetates	Configuration of the C-3 proton	Nature of the NMR signal	Position of the signal (δ in ppm)
Putryl acetate(V) ²	α -equatorial	Triplet(1H)	4.90
3 α -Acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)ene(IV)	β -axial	Multiplet(1H)	4.62
Roxburgholone acetate(VI) ⁷	β -axial	Multiplet	4.60
3 α -Acetoxyfriedoolean-7-ene(VII) ⁹	β -axial	Multiplet	4.60
Friedelanyl acetate(VIII) ⁷	β -axial	Multiplet	4.62
Epi-friedelanyl acetate(IX) ¹⁰	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.87
3 β -Acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene(V)	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.90
3 β -Acetoxyfriedoolean-7 β -ol(X) ⁶	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.90
3 β -Acetoxyfriedoolean-7-ene(XI) ⁹	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.89

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. NMR spectra were taken at 270 MHz for solutions in deuteriochloroform with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. IR spectra were taken in Nujol.

Putrone (I)², natural putrol (III)² and the acetates (V)², (VI)⁷, (VII)⁹, (VIII)⁷, (IX)¹⁰, (X)⁶ and (XI)⁹ were prepared according to reported procedures.

Preparation of 3 α -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (IV): To a boiling solution of putrone(I; 400 mg) in amyl alcohol (15 ml) was added metallic sodium (600 mg) in small pieces and refluxing was continued until all the sodium dissolved. Excess amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation and the precipitated solid was worked up with ether. Chromatography over a column of silica gel followed by crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded 3 α -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (II; 200 mg), m.p. 229-231°. λ_{\max} 3390 cm^{-1} (OH). (Found: C, 84.37; H, 11.76% and M^+ 412. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.40; H, 11.72% and M^+ 412).

The above compound (II; 100 mg) was acetylated with a mixture of acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) by heating over a steam-bath for 3 hrs. Usual work up afforded a crystalline solid, m.p. 208-212°, which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone afforded colorless needles of 3 α -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (IV; 40 mg), m.p. 215-217°. λ_{\max} 1710, 1225 cm^{-1} (acetate). (Found: C, 81.85; H, 11.04%. M^+ 454. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.88; H, 11.08%. M^+ 454). The above acetate(IV) was also found to be different (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) from the acetate of natural putrol.

Preparation of 3 β -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (V): Putrone (I; 400 mg) was refluxed with a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride in purified¹¹ tetrahydrofuran for 6 hrs. Usual work up

afforded a solid, m.p. 190-194° which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded colorless crystals of 3 β -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (III; 200 mg), m.p. 198-200° and was found to be identical (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with the natural putrol².

The above compound (III; 100 mg) was acetylated with a mixture of acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) by heating over a steam-bath for 3 hrs. Usual work up and chromatography over a column of silica gel afforded a solid, m.p. 212-216°, which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone furnished pure crystals of 3 β -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (V), m.p. 219-222°, which was found to be identical (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with the acetate derived from natural putrol by reported² procedure.

Acknowledgement

We are indebted to Prof. P. K. Bhattacharyya, I. I. Sc., Bangalore and Dr. S. C. Pakrashi, I. I. E. M., Calcutta for the spectral data. We thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of us (S. D.).

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Bamford Stevens Reaction of 3 β -Acetoxy-cholest-5-en-7-one Tosylhydrazone

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Manuscript received 25 November 1980, revised 5 June 1981, accepted 15 July 1981

FORMATION of substitution products on alkaline decomposition of tosylhydrazones of ketones¹ including saturated steroidal ketones² has been reported earlier. The present work describes similar